

ELECTRICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON AEROGELS / PHENOLIC RESIN FOR NANOOMPOSITES

Wei-Jen Chen¹, Ming-Yuan Shen², Yi-Luen Li³, Chin-Lung Chiang⁴,
Ming-Chuen Yip⁵ and Chen-Chi M. Ma^{6*}

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering, National Tsing-Hua University
No. 101, Section 2, Kuang-Fu Road, Hsinchu, Taiwan 30013, R.O.C.
Email: d937716@oz.nthu.edu.tw, web page: <http://www.nthu.edu.tw>

² Department of Aviation Mechanical Engineering, China University of Science and Technology
No.200, Zhonghua St., Hengshan Township, Hsinchu, Taiwan 30013, R.O.C.
Email: hbj678@gmail.com, web page: <http://www.hc.cust.edu.tw>

³ Department of Power Mechanical Engineering, National Tsing-Hua University
No. 101, Section 2, Kuang-Fu Road, Hsinchu, Taiwan 30013, R.O.C.
Email: d550309@yahoo.com.tw, web page: <http://www.nthu.edu.tw>

⁴ Department of Safety, Health and Environmental Engineering
No. 1018, Sec. 6, Taiwan Boulevard, Shalu District, Taichung, Taiwan 43302, R.O.C.
Email: dragon@sunrise.hk.edu.tw, web page: <http://www.hk.edu.tw>

⁵ Department of Power Mechanical Engineering, National Tsing-Hua University
No. 101, Section 2, Kuang-Fu Road, Hsinchu, Taiwan 30013, R.O.C.
Email: mcyip@pme.nthu.edu.tw, web page: <http://www.nthu.edu.tw>

^{6*} Department of Chemical Engineering, National Tsing-Hua University
No. 101, Section 2, Kuang-Fu Road, Hsinchu, Taiwan 30013, R.O.C.
Email: ccma@che.nthu.edu.tw, web page: <http://www.nthu.edu.tw>

Keywords: Environmental effects, Carbon aerogels, Mechanical properties

ABSTRACT

In this study carbon aerogels and phenolic resin were used to prepare nano polymer resin. Poly ethylene oxide (PEO) was used as the modifying agent for phenolic resin, to improve its mechanical properties and surface conductivity. The prepared nano polymer resin and carbon cloth were fabricated by compression molding. The nano-prepreg composite material via ultrasonic impregnation was prepared by the laminate was cut into test pieces to measure its mechanical (tensile, flexural and impact) properties, and surface electrical conductivity. The effect of the temperature and humidity (85 °C/ 168hr and 85°C/ 85%RH/ 168 hr) on the mechanical properties were investigated.

Results reveal that the surface conductivity increased by 64.55%, the tensile strength measured at room temperature increased by 35.7%, the flexural strength increased by 18.4%, and the impact strength increased by 101%. In a hot environment (85°C/168hr), the tensile strength was reduced by 23.8%; the flexural strength was increased by 3.1%, and the impact strength was increased by 84.6%. In a high temperature-high humidity environment (85°C/ 85%RH/ 168hr), the tensile strength was reduced by 29.6%; the flexural strength was increased by 17%, and the impact strength was increased by 95.7%.

Keywords: Environmental effects, Carbon aerogels, Mechanical properties, Electrical properties

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoset phenolic resin contains several benzene rings, hence, it has a rigid structure. Since benzene rings are separated by large gaps, when an external force is applied, it is transferred around these gaps. Therefore, the tenacity of such phenolic resin is poor. PEO is a highly crystalline water-soluble polymer. It has been used as the modifying agent for cross-linking polyelectrolyte, promoting the formation of films of electrolyte, improving their mechanical properties, and reducing the crystallinity of polymers. Its molecular chain contains repeating units of two carbon molecules and one oxygen molecule. The main chain of PEO contains ether group (-O-) or soft-chain segments, and the ether radical and the OH radical of the phenolic resin can form hydrogen bonds, increasing intermolecular compatibility, promoting adhesion and enhancing toughness [4-8].

Most recent investigations of carbon aerogels were focused on their thermal properties and adsorbability. The present study investigates the synergistic effects of carbon aerogels [1-3], with various proportions contents (0, 0.025, 0.1, 0.25 Phr), PEO (0.5 Phr) modified phenolic resin and carbon cloth in nano-composite. The effects of the temperature and humidity of the environment on surface electrical conductivity and mechanical properties of such a nano-composite were investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material

Thermosetting phenolic resin (PF-650), Resol Type, Viscosity 150 cps/25 °C, solids 62 %, exothermic Temperature 160~200 °C, was supplied by the Chang Chun Plastics Co., Ltd. Taiwan; Carbon fiber (WCC 3C0401), woven, 3K was obtained from sigma Co., Ltd.. Poly (ethylene oxide), ($[\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}]_n$), mp= 66°C, M.W = 200.000, was supplied by Union Carbide Co., U.S.A. ; Carbon aerogels, surface area 850 m²/g, pore volume 2.3 cm³/g, pore size 20 nm, particle size 8 nm, were supplied by Niching Industrial Co., Ltd. Taiwan.

2.2 Preparation

The samples were prepared as follows. 1) Carbon cloth and carbon aerogels were put in an oven to remove all of the moisture at 120°C/2hr.; 2) carbon aerogels were dispersed in a known proportion in acetone solution; using a magnetic stirrer to stir for 20 minutes, and ultrasonically vibrate for 10 minutes to disperse the carbon aerogels uniformly in the solvent; 3) the phenolic resin was poured slowly into the solution contains carbon aerogels, and dispersed it by mechanical stirring for eight hours; 4) the PEO modifying agent was dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (THF) and poured slowly into the phenolic resin; 5) the uniformly mixed liquor that contains carbon aerogels was poured into the impregnation tank, the ratio of resin to fiber is 6:4, and then add to the carbon fiber cloth of fixed size to disperse the mixed liquor contains carbon aerogel into the carbon cloth by sonication [26], with an impregnation time of 30 min; 6) the immersed fiber cloth was placed in the oven and baked at 75°C for six hours to remove excess solvent and to prepare nano-prepreg contains plies carbon aerogels; 7) the finished nano-prepregs were stacked into layers that each laminate of contains ten prepreg, and place all of them in the mold; the mold was preheated for five minutes, and the nano composites were compression moulded at 175°C and 1000 psi for 30 minutes.

2.3 Test Methods

1. Electrical conductivity test: The four-point probe resistance tester is used to apply a voltage and current to the specimens whose resistances were measured. The voltage and current are measured at the other end of the specimens. The volume resistance, ρ , is obtained using Ohm's law ($\rho = V/I \times W$). Correction factors were applied since the distance between the probes varies with the shape and thickness of the test specimens [9-13]. 2. The hot environment test conditions are 85°C/168 hr, and the high temperature-high humidity environment test conditions are 85°C/85RH/168 hr. 3. The mechanical property tests are performed following ASTM D 3039, ASTM D 790 and ASTM D256.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 show the field emission scanning electron microscopic image of carbon aerogels that formed a loose structure of micro-sized particles. Figure 2 presents the TEM images. Figure 3 presents carbon aerogels that were made by combining more microscopic particles in a three-dimensional structure. Like a sponge, they have are porous and low-density, and has a high specific surface area (with an average particle size of around 10-20 nm). Carbon aerogels have many pores unlike two-dimensional CNTs. Figure 3 clearly reveals that carbon aerogels have structures similar to the three-dimensional structure of a sponge; covered with nano-pores, and therefore exhibit excellent adsorption capacity and depolarization. Hence, liquid impregnation method and ultrasonic oscillation Method were used. The micro-aperture stopped by the external forces that are generated by crack growth, increase the mechanical strength and also improve the electrical conductivity.

Figure.1 SEM of Carbon aerogels for Surface structure

Figure.2 TEM of Carbon aerogels for Surface structure

Figure.3 TEM of Carbon aerogels for Surface structure

3.1 Electrical conductivity characterization

The conductivity of the nano composite increases. With the increasing of conducting material. When the amount of added filler reaches the percolation threshold, the conductivity increases sharply. When this threshold is exceeded, adding more conducting material rapidly increase the conductivity [14-16]. As summarized Table 1 and Figure 4, by adding a small amount of a carbon aerogel (0.025 Phr) causes increase conductivity 509.64S/cm. As the carbon aerogel content increases to 0.25 Phr, the conductivity increases to 802.8 S/cm. Carbon fibers conduct effectively in their axial direction. Therefore, adding carbon aerogels increases the conductivity in the vertical direction of the fibers. Hence, carbon fibers and carbon aerogels form a complete conductive path inside the resin substrate. As a modifying agent for phenolic resin, PEO is a highly-crystalline water-soluble polymer. It is mostly used as polymer electrolyte in batteries [4-7]. It transfers electrons effectively along the conductive path. Phenolic resin is amorphous and very compatible with PEO, it improves the mechanical properties of resin. For a give carbon aerogels content (0.25 Phr), by adding (PEO, 0.5 Phr) modifying agent to phenolic resin increases its electrical conductivity by 64.55% (838.63 S/cm).

3.2 Environmental conditions and mechanical properties

3.2.1 Tensile strength characterization

The mechanical property was first tested at room temperature. Then test specimen were placed in a high temperature and high temperature-high humidity environments to test their mechanical strength again. The effects of moisture on the material characteristics of the composites are as follows. Increasing the moisture content of the resin substrate reduces the glass transition temperature T_g ; increases the plasticity ; reduces the thermal residual stress, and reduces the interlaminar shear strength [17-20]. Figure 5 shows the tensile strength data obtained in the special environment. The tensile strength at room temperature increases with the carbon aerogel content. At the same content (0.25 Phr), the tensile strength of the modified phenolic resin is increased to 607.7 MPa, by 35.76%. The ultrasonic impregnation method was applied to cause resin to penetrate the gaps among fibers [25],

generating a preferred bonding force between the phenolic resin and the carbon fiber. When the second reinforcing carbon aerogels is added, their sponge-like structure promotes the absorption of forces. In particular when brittle failure grows: cracks grow has a preferred bearing capacity. The complete filling by carbon aerogels into the pores among substrates forms preferred joints between resin and fiber, improving the tensile strength.

Table. 1 Surface conductivity of nanocomposite with variety carbon aerogel contents

Carbon aerogels content (Phr)	Electrical conductivity (S/cm)
0	0
0.025	510
0.1	596
0.25	803
0.25*	839

*Modified phenolic resin

Figure.4 Electrical conductivity of carbon aerogels added with different percentages.

Figure.5 Tensile strength of carbon aerogels added with different percentages.

Tensile strength was also measured at high temperature, 85°C/168 hour, which slightly declines as the content of carbon aerogels increases. When the carbon aerogel content was 0.25 Phr, the tensile strength of the modified phenolic resin was 343.7 MPa. Since phenolic resin ($39 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$) and carbon fiber ($3\sim 5 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$) have different coefficient of thermal expansion which are different environment [20] over the long-term at high temperature, the number of microcracks between the phenolic resin substrates and the carbon fibers increases, and they extend along the substrate-fiber interface. However, the cracks in the test pieces that have not been exposed to a high temperature grow along the inside of the substrate. Although the carbon aerogels can retards the growth of cracks, the sharp increase in the number of microcracks results reduces the tensile strength.

The tensile strength at high temperature and high humidity (85°C -85 RH/168 hour) declines markedly (286.3 MPa). For a particular content (0.25 Phr), the tensile strength of the modified phenolic resin was decreased (263.6 MPa). In this environment that is supersaturated with moisture, the carbon fibers and carbon aerogels, which were originally in a dry environment absorbed much moisture, causing expansion or shrinkage, The stress-strain that is generated produced by this phenomenon accelerates the formation of microcracks inside substrates and degrades the resin substrate [21-24]. When the phenolic resin is in a supersaturated moist environment, the adhesive force of the resin was reduced, and shrinkage may occur in the direction of the pressure, and generate microcracks. These phenomena will reduce the tensile strength of composite material.

3.2.2 Flexural strength characterization

Figure 6 illustrates the flexural strength data measured in the hot-humid environment. The flexural strength at room temperature increases with the carbon aerogels content. At the carbon aerogel content was 0.25 Phr, flexural strength of the modified phenolic resin was increased from 353.3 to 455.5 MPa, and the flexural strength was increased by 18.34%. The flexural strength after treatment at high temperature, 85°C/168 hour, declines to 353.3 MPa (0 Phr) as the carbon aerogels content increases, and the flexural strength is increased by 5.57 % (373 MPa). At the carbon aerogel content was 0.25 Phr, the enhancement of the flexural strength of the modified phenolic resin was increased by only 3.11 % (364.3 MPa). Accordingly, the special structure that exists at a particular carbon aerogel content can withstand large shrinkage in the direction pressure.

For the flexural strength test at high temperature and high humidity (85°C -85RH/168 hour) environment, the flexural strength of neat resin is reduced to 350.9 MPa (0 Phr) as the carbon aerogel increases, and the flexural strength is increased by 12.4 % (394.5 MPa). For carbon aerogel content of 0.25 Phr, the flexural strength of the modified phenolic resin is reduced to 299.9 MPa. PEO modifying agent forms netty crystals in the phenolic resin [4,5]. Although it improves the mechanical properties of the phenolic resin, over the long-term at high temperature and in a supersaturated moist environment, hydrogen and oxygen combine to form long chain of -OH- radicals, which reduces the mechanical properties greatly.

Figure.6 Flexural strength of carbon aerogels added with different percentages.

Figure.7 Impact strength of carbon aerogels added with different percentages.

3.2.3 Impact strength characterization

Figure 7 shows the impact strength measured at temperature-humidity environment. The impact strength at room temperature increased with carbon aerogels content. For carbon aerogel content of 0.25 Phr, the impact strength of the modification of the phenolic resin increases to 222.35 J/m by 101.7 %.

The phenolic resin contains several benzene rings, it is relatively rigid. The benzene rings form gaps in its structure. When an external force is applied, it is transferred around the gaps among the loosely arranged molecules, so the tenacity is poor. Intermolecular hydrogen bonds are formed in phenolic resins when a PEO modifying agent is added, the soft molecular chains of PEO shuttle in the gaps between the phenolic resin molecules, reducing the free volume among them, lengthening the destruction and path of transmission of the external force, promoting the absorption of force, and thereby, toughening the material. Additionally, the special nano-structure of carbon aerogels and nanomicro-pores effectively absorb the excess force, greatly increasing the impact strength.

When the test specimens were treated at high temperature 85°C/168 hour, the impact strength of neat resin increased from 98.19 J/m (0 Phr) as the carbon aerogels content increases, and the impact strength is increased by 14.98% (112.9 J/m). The temperature does not significantly affect the impact strength. According to Figure 3,

the three-dimensional nano-structure and nano-pores can effectively absorb the energy the results from the external forces, slowing the transfer of those external forces and the formation of cracks. At a particular carbon aerogels content (0.25 Phr), the impact strength of the modified phenolic resin was increased 84.76 % (181.42 J/m). Clearly, temperature does not affect the tenacity of the nano-composite.

At high temperature and high humidity (85°C -85RH/168 hour), the impact strength inaeased to 94.9 J/m (0 Phr) as the content of carbon aerogels increases, increased by 12.4 % (127.78 J/m). At room temperature, the moisture only slightly affects the damage to initial energy absorption, subsequent energy absorption and the size of the damaged area [25]. The penetration of moisture reduces the anchoring strength in the joint between the resin and the carbon fibers. Adding, carbon aerogel can reduce the formation of microcracks in the joint. The loose structure can absorb excess moisture to form a capsular structure that contains it. The impact energy in the nano-composite can be absorbed and dispersed uniformly to reduce the effect of energy concentration. At a particular content (0.25 Phr), the impact strength of the modified phenolic resin is increased from 181.42J/m to 186.03 J/m. The PEO modifying agent forms a netty crystal structure in phenolic resin that prevents any influence moisture on and promotes the absorption and dispersion of energy.

4 CONCLUSIONS

By adding a suitable amount of carbon aerogels in the polymer matrix can cause complete conductive paths inside carbon fibers and resin substrates. PEO can improve the mechanical properties of phenolic resin, and can also increase electrical conductivity. At room temperature, as the content of carbon aerogels increases, the mechanical strength increases, Adding PEO also improves the mechanical strength. Over a long period of testing in a hot environment and or at a hot and humid environment, the tensile strength and the flexural strength decrease greatly, regardless of whether PEO or carbon aerogels have been added. Carbon fibers and carbon aerogels expand or shrink in different directions in the presence of supersaturated moisture, and the stress-strain will cause acceleration of the formation of microcracks within the substrate as well as the deterioration of the resin substrate. Additionally, hydrogen bonds between phenolic resin, oxygen atoms will form long chains of -OH-radicals, accelerating the deterioration of mechanical properties. However when PEO is added, the impact strength will be increased, since PEO forms a netty crystal structure in the phenolic resin that prevents moisture from affecting it and promotes the absorption and dispersion of energy.

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